

Clean Sky 2 Programme

10th April 2019

CS Event @ The Hotel

IADP Large Passenger Aircraft
WP3 (Platform 3)

Next generation aircraft cockpit systems and avionics

Disruptive Cockpit for Large Aircraft

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New aircraft cockpit systems and avionics

Overall Objectives

Intuitive and multimodal pilot interfaces

Aircraft Status, pilot health and behavior monitoring

Systems management improvement

Enhanced cockpit

Disruptive cockpit

Reduced crew workload

Augmented vision for approach assistance

Enhanced mission management

Continuous Auto pilot, available in any flight condition

Large Aircraft Disruptive Cockpit

Project objectives

Bring to TRL5 innovative and disruptive cockpit functions and technologies for Large Aircraft Single Pilot Operational concept by 2023

Safety Enhancement

- ❖ Enhanced situation awareness
- ❖ High integrity autonomous systems
- ❖ Improved fatigue and incapacitation management

Human-System Teaming

- ❖ Improved Human-System dialogue, user experience
- ❖ Assisted Human decision making
- ❖ Autonomous Systems executing

Environmentally friendly

- ❖ Fuel burn reduction functions
- ❖ Optimized 4D trajectories
- ❖ Optimized volume and shape for fuel burn reduction

Adaptable cockpit

- ❖ Built-in connectivity
- ❖ Easily upgradable, low cost
- ❖ Applicative cockpit

Large Aircraft Disruptive Cockpit Project Scope

Define and deliver.....

....Innovative cockpit functions and enabling technologies....

Ground Obstacle and runway detection

Cockpit Display System and Flight Management

Cockpit Utility Management System

ATC Speech To Text (Voice recognition)

New navigation sensors GPAHRS, LIDAR

With CS2 Members and Partners

Tactile Control Panel (LAPARTS)

Image Based Landing (IMBALS)

Li Fi connectivity (ALC)

Large Aircraft Disruptive Cockpit Project Scope

Integrate, Verify and Validate...

....Selected functions and technologies...

In Flight test

In DISCO Systems integration
ground demonstrator

In DISCO Operational ground
Demonstrator

Large Aircraft Disruptive Cockpit

On the way to TRL 5

Proof of Concept

TRL5

Systems demonstrator
Integration completed

New nav. Sensors flight tests
campaign preparation on A350

First Systems integration test bench set-up complete and first displays and FMS functions integrated and tested

Some Functions prototypes under operational evaluation

First New Navigation sensors flight tests campaign on Airbus A330

Partners projects contracted and started

2015

2016

2017

2018

2019

2020

2021

2022

2023

New aircraft cockpit systems and avionics

A European collaborative impact

Thank you for your participation !

